

Oil Pipeline Leak Detection and Control using Optimal Filtering and LSTM

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Abstract—There are many refinery industries in Beaumont, Texas, and gas pipeline leak detection is the great business challenge. In the world, every 2 minutes there is a leak in the pipeline and more than 40 billion dollars have been unutilized for this impeding task. Therefore, oil pipeline leak detection and control is a critical business issue to prevent environmental hazards, economic losses, and public concerns. This paper presents an oil pipeline leak detection and control framework that incorporates optimal filtering and LSTM networks. The proposed technique leverages sensor data from SCADA/IoT platforms to properly estimate pipeline states, and provide real-time control commands. Moreover, the online learning framework is introduced to adapt the model to evolving pipeline conditions. Numerical Simulation results show the effectiveness of the developed approach. Hopefully, this framework and analysis will be significantly helpful to the education and industries. The spatial and temporal features with the hurricane and tornado will be considered in this model and analysis the impacts.

Index Terms—Kalman Filter, Leak Detection, LSTM Networks, Hybrid Fault Diagnosis, Pipeline.

I. INTRODUCTION

The industrial cyber-physical systems such as oil and gas networks, water pipelines, refineries, chemical plants, and smart grid are faced huge operational and maintenance challenges [1], [2]. These business issues can significantly impact in the Southwest Texas specifically Beaumont area due to spatial and temporal features, flood, hurricane and tornado [3], [4]. On the other hand, there is a significant cornered and limitation about the real-time data a collection and analysis so the mathematical modeling can play an important role [5]. The sensors network, cellular infrastructure and machine learning can also play role for properly monitoring, control, and analysis of these cyber-physical systems [6], [7], [8]. In summary, the early and reliable leak detection as well as control in this framework is the key business issue in this mission critical ecosystem as shown in Fig. 1. This can not only impact to the financial loss but also safety and environmental concerns. Driven by these motivations, this paper presents an oil pipeline leak detection and control framework that incorporates optimal filtering and machine learning framework. Numerical Simulation results show the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

There have been some existing methods, laboratory and sensors network based pipeline leak detection and monitoring

Fig. 1: Proposed pipeline leak detection system framework.

frameworks in the literature. To begin with, the differential equation and advanced mathematical theory based pipeline leak modeling framework is proposed in [5]. Moreover, Kalman filtering (KF) has been used for pipeline state estimation [9], [10]. Hybrid systems after combining model-based KF estimation with machine learning such as LSTM are now emerging as a promising research approach, offering both interpretability and adaptive system performance. This paper presents an oil pipeline leak detection and control approach that integrates KF and LSTM networks. The developed technique leverages sensor data from SCADA/IoT platforms to properly estimate pipeline states, and provide real-time control commands. Furthermore, the online learning process is introduced to adapt the model to evolving pipeline conditions. Extensive Simulation results show the effectiveness of the proposed method.

II. CONSIDERED PROBLEM STATEMENT AND TECHNOLOGY

This paper addresses the problem of oil pipeline leak detection and control as shown in Fig. 2. The pipeline system dynamics are nonlinear, noisy, and partially observed through a set of sensors measuring pressure, flow, temperature, valve position, pump speed, and friction coefficient. Leaks manifest as deviations in true state variables, which must be estimated and classified accurately within short period of time. The challenge is to design a holistic approach that integrates optimal filtering, data-driven leak classification, and adaptive control as shown in Fig. 1. Without handling these issued it can not only impact the all business but also people as well

Key Aspect	Description
Key questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to detect leaks accurately and in real-time oil pipeline? - How to integrate physics-based models with data-driven learning? - How to adapt detection and control methods dynamically?
Approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State-space modeling and Kalman filtering for estimation - LSTM networks for sequential leak classification - Adaptive thresholding and online learning
Technology impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhanced safety and reliability of pipeline operations - Integration of IoT/SCADA data with intelligent algorithms - Reduced environmental risks via timely detection - Supports real-time decision making and automation
Significance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advances hybrid model-data leak detection - Scalable solutions for industrial monitoring - Bridges control theory and AI methods - Foundation for adaptive, intelligent infrastructure

Fig. 2: Key aspects, challenges and technologies.

as safety and national security concerned. In the following section, we will describe the oil pipeline system dynamics.

III. OIL PIPELINE SYSTEM DYNAMICS

The pipeline system is modeled using a discrete-time state-space framework with a leak disturbance as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{E}_l\mathbf{d}(t) + \mathbf{w}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{F}_l\mathbf{d}(t) + \mathbf{v}(t) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the system states (pressure, flow, temperature, valve position, pump speed, friction coefficient) at time t , $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the control inputs (valve position, pump speed), $\mathbf{d}(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the leak input, $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the measured outputs (pressure, flow, valve position), $\mathbf{w}(t)$, and $\mathbf{v}(t)$ are the Gaussian distributed process and measurement noise. The key matrices and their values such as \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{F} are given below:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.90 & 0.05 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 \\ 0.04 & 0.85 & 0.05 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 \\ 0.00 & 0.03 & 0.88 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 \\ 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.92 & 0.06 & 0.00 \\ 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.03 & 0.90 & 0.00 \\ 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.00 & 0.95 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.05 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.1 \\ 0.1 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{E}_l = \begin{bmatrix} -0.3 \\ -0.1 \\ 0.0 \\ 0.0 \\ 0.0 \\ 0.0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}_l = \begin{bmatrix} -0.25 \\ -0.1 \\ 0.0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Based on these unobservable pipeline states (valve position, pump speed, friction coefficient) and noisy environments, we will need to apply optimal filtering approach to know all state variables as shown in Fig. 1.

IV. PROPOSED OPTIMAL FILTERING AND LSTM APPROACH

The proposed pipeline leak detection algorithm integrates an optimal Kalman filter (KF)-based state estimator [11], [12] with an LSTM as shown in Fig. 3 and algorithm (below). It adaptively thresholds residuals from the KF to detect anomalies while leveraging LSTM predictions for improved leak classification [6], [13], [14].

Fig. 3: Flow diagram of the proposed system framework.

- 1: Initialize, $t \leftarrow 0$
- 2: Set $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(0) \leftarrow \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$, $P(0) \leftarrow P_0$, $u(0) \leftarrow u_0$, $R \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 3: **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
- 4: $y(t)$ ▷ KF Prediction Step
- 5: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(t) \leftarrow \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t-1) + \mathbf{B}u(t-1)$
- 6: $P^-(t) \leftarrow \mathbf{A}P(t-1)\mathbf{A}^\top + \mathbf{Q}$ ▷ KF Correction Step
- 7: $y_{\text{pred}}(t) \leftarrow \mathbf{C}\hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(t)$
- 8: $S(t) \leftarrow \mathbf{C}P^-(t)\mathbf{C}^\top + \mathbf{R}$
- 9: $K(t) \leftarrow P^-(t)\mathbf{C}^\top S(t)^{-1}$
- 10: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) \leftarrow \hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(t) + K(t)(y(t) - y_{\text{pred}}(t))$
- 11: $P(t) \leftarrow (\mathbf{I} - K(t)\mathbf{C})P^-(t)$ ▷ Residual Computation & Adaptive Thresholding
- 12: $res(t) \leftarrow \|y(t) - y_{\text{pred}}(t)\|_2$
- 13: Append $res(t)$ to R

14: Calculate adaptive threshold:

$$thr(t) \leftarrow \mu_R + \alpha\sigma_R$$

15: **if** $res(t) > thr(t)$ **then**

16: Generate leak alert (KF) at time t

17: **end if**

▷ LSTM-Based Leak Detection

18: Extract windowed features from recent data

19: $p_{leak}(t) \leftarrow \text{LSTM.predict}(\text{features})$

20: **if** $p_{leak}(t) > p_{threshold}$ **then**

21: Generate leak alert (LSTM) at time t

22: **end if**

▷ Optional LSTM Model Online Update

23: **if** update conditions met **then**

24: Update LSTM model with buffered data

25: **end if**

▷ Control Law

26: $e(t) \leftarrow r - \hat{x}_{\text{pressure}}(t)$

27: $u(t) \leftarrow u(t-1) + K_c \times e(t)$

▷ Send control $u(t)$ to actuators

28: **end for**

Based the algorithm and steps, the Colab is used for simulation.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the system model and algorithm, the simulation results are demonstrated in Figs. 4- 7. It can be seen that algorithm can be effectively estimated the pipeline states. For example, the pressure, flow, temperature, and valve position are illustrated in Fig. 4. Additionally, the valve position, pump speed, and friction coefficient are illustrated in Fig. 4-6states. The controller performance is illustrated in Fig. 6. Finally, the confusion matrix is demonstrated in Fig. 7. The LSTM model demonstrates 59% overall accuracy.

Fig. 4: Pressure, Flow, Temperature, and Valve Position: True and Estimated.

Fig. 5: Pump Speed, and Friction Coefficient: True and Estimated.

Fig. 6: Controller performance.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a hybrid model-based and data-driven leak detection and control framework for oil pipelines. The integration of KF with adaptive residual thresholds and LSTM networks with online learning enabled robust detection under realistic noise and dynamic conditions. Control feedback is properly maintained operational targets. Future work will extend this approach with nonlinear models and multi-sensor fusion with cyber attacks. The special and temporal correlation with the hurricane and tornado will be considered in this model and analysis the impacts.

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Fig. 7: Confusion matrix.

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